

DEVELOPMENT OF OCCUPATIONAL PERSONALITY INVENTORY

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Development of Occupational Personality Inventory

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Abstract

This study developed an Occupational Personality Inventory (OPI). Specifically, it answered and accomplished the following objectives: (1) To construct items of the proposed Occupational Personality Inventory based on literature and studies. (2) To establish the validity of the proposed Occupational Personality Inventory by: (1.1) Face Validity and (2.2) Content Analysis. (3) To establish the reliability of the proposed Occupational Personality Inventory by Test Re-Test Design. (4) To establish a standardization process of the proposed Occupational Personality Inventory. Research and Development (R&D) was the research method used in the study. Most of the items were found valid after it underwent experts' face validation and Lawshe's content validity method. The items garnered an excellent reliability using test re-test method. A manual was made for the uniformity of administration of the test and consistent scoring of the inventory to guarantee the standardization process. The study's findings led to the conclusions that the items of the created Occupational Personality Inventory evaluated and represented various occupational personalities of the employees; employees were discriminated against based on their occupational personalities according to the items in the scale; every item in the inventory met statistical validity requirements; and the reliability index of the OPI is excellent.

Keywords: *validity, reliability, standardization*

Introduction

Personality is referred to as the enduring traits and behaviours that comprise an individual's subjective way of adjusting to life. Individuals have distinct personalities from birth. We are all unique from one another, which is what gives every one of us a unique quality. The result of environment and heredity—and their regular interactions—is personality. It is the primary reason for individual variations.

Personality is a huge factor in our lives. Personality differences are related to both physical and mental health in terms of well-being. People who score higher on some personality traits and lower on others seem to be in better form, from how content people are with their lives at any given time to matters of life and death. People spend a significant portion of their lives in relationships, therefore socially relevant personality qualities like agreeableness and extroversion are important. Thus, it makes sense that a person's unique personality traits could play a role in determining how well they get along with their romantic partner. Personality traits seem to have a bearing on more traditional types of performance in the realm of success, even if they don't necessarily correlate with longevity and romantic fulfillment. Science has found correlations between people's characteristics and achievements in a variety of domains, including income, job preferences, and grades. Every individual has a unique personality, and people are always attempting to read each other (Damian, 2018).

According to Edelstein (2009), personality is also related to one's appearance. Personality cues can be seen in clothing, facial expressions, and other outward features. For example, smiling and having a lively appearance could indicate that someone is rather outgoing. Appearing well and at ease could suggest emotional stability. According to some psychologists, having distinct eyebrows could be a sign of grandiose narcissism. Psychologists have also discovered evidence linking personality traits to one's environment to some extent. For example, exhibiting a variety of literature was linked to more openness to experience, while having an ordered bedroom was linked to conscientiousness.

Employees with their personality known, also look at their career growth and success. One must know how to fit himself in the workplace considering his personality to reach his goals and aspirations. He must be aware of his characteristics and behavior because he is the controller of it.

A person's personality influences every facet of their performance, including their response to work-related issues. It's crucial to identify personality traits and match workers with tasks that best suit their personalities because not every personality is a good fit for every job position. This can lead to increased productivity and job satisfaction, helping your business function more efficiently (Munroe, 2019).

According to research by Dr. Blaine Landis (2020), understanding one's personality can help an employee modify behavior at work, play to strengths, improve on weaknesses, interact with coworkers more effectively and ultimately lead to career success. Career success is strongly influenced by one's personality. For a variety of reasons, personality matters. Fit—how well a person's personality fits the position, the team, and the business as a whole—is one factor. One of the main reasons for conflict and turnover is poor fit. A person's personality will influence a variety of outcomes, including being employed, promoted, derailed, helping others, and perceived as a leader. Understanding various personality qualities helps foster professional development and improve managers' interactions with staff members.

an employee's, more studies are being conducted to answer the question of how an employee's personality greatly affects work performance. It is still a question of what kind of personality type an employee has so he can suit it best with his work performance.

These claims gave the researcher the idea to conduct a study and encouraged her to look into the topic more. It also spurs her to create a test specifically for Filipino workers, whose personalities have a big impact on how well they do at work. And it necessitates starting the process of creating an Employee Occupational Personality Inventory.

Completing an Occupational Personality Inventory can help one see how personality and work performance are based on various, objective theories rather than being evaluated subjectively. It will give workers an overview of their personality kinds. Their dominating personality will be dichotomously illustrated by posing a series of questions and then rating the answers. They will be better able to identify and comprehend their own personalities and apply methods that work best for them. This raises the standard and effectiveness of work output.

Employees' personality has more influence in work than they may realize. Their dominant personality guides the way they perform at work and how they socialize at work.

The creation of this exam will open the door for a practical tool to be used in the workplace, one that can predict job performance and fit between the employer and candidates. The test will solicit information about employees' characteristics and behavior- their style of interacting with people and situations, emotional make-up, interests, preferences, and motivations. The result of the test will be beneficial in suiting the applicant's personality for a specific job- increasing employee satisfaction and efficiency and reducing the company's turnover rate. This is Tarlac City's first personality test, created as a pre-employment tool to help companies match the appropriate candidate with the right position and to help candidates find the position that best fits them. This will also contribute to the Province of Tarlac's declining unemployment rate.

As it evaluates various occupational personalities, the study, according to the researcher, will be beneficial to psychology in general and the industrial setting in particular since it will provide a foundation for creating strategies and programs that are most appropriate for the workers. Additionally, the researcher thinks that this study will serve as a tool for a deeper comprehension of human undertakings and advance both our industry and individual advancement.

Research Objectives

This research aimed to develop an Occupational Personality Inventory. It specifically sought to answer and accomplish the following objectives:

1. To construct items of the proposed Occupational Personality Inventory based on literature and studies.
2. To establish the validity of the proposed Occupational Personality Inventory by:
 - 2.1. Face Validity
 - 2.2. Content Analysis
3. To establish the reliability of the proposed Occupational Personality Inventory by Test Re-Test Design.
4. To establish a standardization process of the proposed Occupational Personality Inventory.

Literature Review

Personality has to do with individual differences among people in behavior patterns, cognition and emotion. Personality can be conceptualized using personality traits. Personality traits are enduring personal characteristics that are revealed in a particular pattern of behavior in a variety of situations. Personality has a significant impact on behavior so on performance of individual in any domain. There are many organizational parameters like job performance, job satisfaction, leadership qualities etc. where personality traits play a significant role. Various national and international research papers conceptualize personality and personality traits and those which establish relationship between personality traits and performance. Wide parameters like job performance, job satisfaction, leadership, employability etc. are always taken into consideration. Most articles show that conscientiousness and emotional stability consistently predict job performance for all job types. In addition, some have suggested that personality is useful for predicting other work-related criteria, like job satisfaction and job performance (Khan, 2017).

Personality traits are aspects of personality that are relatively stable over time, differ across individuals and are relatively consistent over situations (Anusic & Schimmack, 2016). Probably the most common framework to the research of personality traits is the Big Five. The Big Five trait taxonomy is a hierarchical model of personality traits with five broad factors, which represent personality at the broadest level of abstraction. These factors are Neuroticism, Extraversion, Openness to Experience, Agreeableness, and Conscientiousness. Each factor describes a broad domain of psychological functioning that is composed from a set of more specific and narrow traits (Roberts et al, 2006). Several scholars have argued that personality traits, processes and behaviors should be separated from each other in order to increase our understanding of how personality explains behaviors (Baumert et al, 2017; Zeigler-Hill et al, 2019). In this perspective, personality traits can be seen as basic tendencies or general predispositions, largely controlled by biological influences (McCrae & Costa, 2008; McCrae, 2018). In contrast, motivational processes, such as preferences, as well as subsequent behaviors, represent the interaction between personality traits and the specifics of the social context. As such, processes and behaviors

give contextualized form to what it means to possess certain relatively broad and abstract personality traits (Cantor, 1990; McAdams & Pals, 2006; McCrae & Costa, 2008; Wood et al, 2015; McCrae, 2018). Preferences, therefore, can be seen as being a consequence of inherent personality traits. These preferences will, in turn, affect a person's behavior. Specifically, an individual's behavioral displays are expected to follow the law of effect: a certain behavior increases when it satisfies a person's needs and desires, and a certain behavior decreases when it does not (Wood et al, 2015). That is, a certain behavior will be displayed more often if that behavior is congruent with a person's preferences (Christiansen & Tett, 2008). All in all, one could argue that personality traits affect a person's preferences, and that these preferences will guide that person's behavior in such a way that it will be beneficial and satisfying to the person.

Personality is not an excuse for poor performance, but managers can use what they know about a direct report's personality to create growth opportunities and get more out of the employee. Employees and managers can use what they know about their personalities to discuss opportunities for changing the nature of a worker's tasks, providing team-building opportunities and placing employees in optimal positions that allow them to thrive. It can give you insights to have those conversations, so you can anticipate where they may want to make changes so that everyone is successful. It is in managers' best interests to incorporate a range of personalities on their teams. And understanding the nuances of different personalities can help managers bring out the best in their workers (Landis, 2020).

Psychological distress in the workplace is usually attributed to work-related variables (i.e. physical and psychological demands, irregular schedules, and workplace harassment) and non-work-related variables (i.e. family structure, support available from social networks outside of work). Even though work-related variables could be stressful, their effect does not seem to uniformly affect all workers. Individuals working in the same organization could differ in terms of their appraisal of work demands and in coping strategies used to face them. Based on those individual differences, high job demands may not necessarily result in job strain for all workers. For instance, conscientiousness and neuroticism are both important personality traits. Additionally, agreeableness, conscientiousness, openness and emotional stability (also termed high neuroticism) moderated the negative impact of a high workload (Saade et al., 2021).

In the past decade, important advances have taken place in the study of the role of personality in predicting work performance. First, the accumulation of research on personality contributed to the development of a taxonomy, the Big Five, which makes essential personality characteristics clearer. Second, psychometrically sound tools for assessing personality in the work place and for analyzing jobs in terms of necessary personality traits have been developed. In parallel, a more systematic consideration of work requirements and a better understanding of factors important for work performance have allowed for a clearer definition of the potential roles for personality in this context (Touze, 2015).

Healthy and motivated employees are essential for the productivity and success of a company and for reducing financial burden on the health care system and society. Consequently, research and practice aim to define and create healthy and motivating work environments in which employees get what they need to thrive in their work. Indeed, employees are well-suited for and perform best in their work if it fulfills basic human needs, such as the need for autonomy, competence, and relatedness (Deci & Ryan, 2000). In addition to these basic needs, employees also have unique needs related to their personality and values (Van Vianen, Hamstra, & Koen, 2016). Person-Environment fit theory (Van Vianen, 2018) proposes that people have an innate need to fit environments that match their own characteristics. A specific work environment can be thriving for one employee and oppressing for another, depending on an employee's personality (Herr et al, 2021).

Depending on a person's traits, some career roles will seem more attractive and desirable than others. If a certain career role is preferred, people will start to behave in a way that will allow them to engage in that role. Engaging in the role is likely to be intrinsically satisfying, because people are likely to feel good about being able to express their traits in their work environments. Arguably, certain roles allow people to express their traits more than others. Therefore, although restrictions by external demands or expectations can always occur, in general people's preferences will influence their role-taking behavior or their role enactment (Parker et al., 2010; De Jong et al, 2014).

The test's item building will be based on the identification of personality traits related to work performance, which will be achieved by merging the many theories and concepts of the scholars previously mentioned. Moreover, it will help achieve the goals of the entire research project.

Methodology

Participants

The participants for this study were white collar job workers with age ranges from eighteen (18) to sixty (60) years old taken from samples that was determined through stratified convenient sampling. This study is limited only to the employees of Classic Baker Corporation during the year 2023- 2024. The total population of the white collared workers was one hundred sixty (160) employees. Sixty (60) employees were subjected to test re-test of the validated initial inventory. One hundred (100) employees underwent the test re-test of the final inventory. All were eighteen (18) to sixty (60) years old at the time of testing.

Instrument

The Development of the Occupational Personality Inventory underwent processes such as development, validation, reliability testing, and standardization. The development was done with the expertise of the subject-matter experts; face validity and Lawshe's content validity were used in validation; for reliability, the researcher used test re-test using Pearson Coefficient of Correlation; and for standardization, to ensure the uniformity of procedure, a manual was created for the administration and scoring of the inventory.

Development

The test items for the initial edition of the questionnaire were created by the researchers based on their own experiences as well as a review of relevant studies, theories, and literature. The Occupational Personality Inventory's sections were developed before the inventory's items were created. The Occupational Personality Inventory's initial formulation involved extracting its sections from many relevant theories, studies, and literature. The developed regions of personality served as the foundation for the test structures. It was assessed by specialists. Along with the first inventory, each expert offered recommendations. They selected the items they thought best reflected the traits or indicators found in the Occupational Personality Inventory. Blank slots were included at the end of the checklist so that the experts could add any new traits or recommendations.

Items were adjusted, improved, and reorganized following the experts' review of the first inventory and the completion of the content validity ratio. The inventory was then put through a test-retest procedure. Subsequently, the items were ranked in order of validity and reliability. To assess the final inventory's dependability, it underwent one more test and retest. The researcher then created a handbook to instruct the examiners on how to administer and interpret the test.

Validation

Face Validity and Content Validity

Items were put in a table of specifications for the first draft of the inventory to make sure they were adequate or sufficient in each personality domain. Every item was categorized in a dichotomous fashion based on the ten (10) personality domains to which it was represented. Twenty-five (25) items total are included in each dichotomous domain (extraversion versus introversion, neuroticism versus stability, sensing versus intuition, judging versus perceiving, and extrinsic versus intrinsic). Experts evaluated the included items for face and content validity to make necessary corrections and improvements to the test items. Items that were deemed irrelevant were removed, and relevant items were added at the experts' or evaluators' suggestion based on the Lawshe's content validity method. Valid items were incorporated into the second draft of the test. Furthermore, the Occupational Personality Inventory's structure, page layout, and guidelines were changed to better serve the target audience. The inventory then moved forward for testing.

Reliability

Test-retest reliability was applied to the second draft, and the Pearson Coefficient of Correlation was utilized to gauge its quality. Reliability-tested items were added to the inventory's final draft. Using the Pearson Coefficient of Correlation, the finalized draft's reliability was tested and retested.

Standardization

The researcher developed a manual to introduce occupational personality to both the test administrator and the respondents to ensure consistency in the methods used to administer and score the proposed Occupational Personality Inventory for employees. The produced examiner's handbook was turned in to be tested for substance, economy, administrability, usability, and scorability.

Ethical Considerations

The following ethical guidelines were observed and prioritized for the research period:

- The respondents gave their free will to participate in the study. The study participants are free to leave at any time if they want.
- Prior to the study, the subjects gave their full consent. This required the researcher to offer participants enough information and guarantees about the study so they could comprehend the ramifications of taking part and make an informed, deliberate, and free choice about whether to participate, free from coercion or pressure.
- The data and information that were obtained from the participants were treated with utmost confidentiality.
- There was no harm done to research participants in any way.
- All research-related communications were conducted in an open and sincere manner, and false information will not be shared.

Results and Discussion

Development of Occupational Personality Inventory based on Literature and Studies

The investigator conducted a thorough examination and analysis of various studies and literature about occupational personality. These included the written works, theoretical frameworks, and empirical studies that made a substantial contribution to the creation of the Occupational Personality Inventory. These provided as the foundation and guidelines for creating the inventory's objects. One hundred

twenty-five (125) items in all were created using relevant studies and literature as a basis. Books, journals, research studies, and the internet were the sources of this connected literature and studies. The collected data served as a valuable resource for the researcher during the conduct and enhancement of the investigation.

Initial Inventory

Every item in the first inventory fit into a single statement. Five dichotomous domains are included in the initial form of the test: Extroversion vs. Introversion, Sensing vs. Intuition, Judging vs. Perceiving, Stability vs. Neuroticism, and Extrinsic vs. Intrinsic Motivation. There are twenty-five (25) items in the test's initial draft for each dichotomous domain. In summary, the initial draft of the Occupational Personality measured a total of one hundred twenty-five (125) elements. Local conditions were taken into consideration while modifying items from occupational personality study. Similarly, the researcher created other items with an objective foundation from literature.

Table 1. Sources of Items

Domains of Learning Preference Schedule	Initial Inventory		Total Items
	Related Literature	Related Studies	
Extraversion vs. Introversion a. Extraversion Statements b. Introversion Statements	1, 11, 26, 31, 36, 41, 46, 51, 61, 66, 71, 76, 81, 86, 91, 96, 101, 106, 111, 116, 121	6, 16, 21, 56	25
Stability vs. Neuroticism a. Stability Statements b. Neuroticism Statements	2, 7, 12, 17, 27, 32, 42, 47, 52, 57, 67, 72, 77, 87, 92, 97, 102, 107, 112, 117, 122	22, 37, 62, 82	25
Sensory vs. Intuition a. Sensory Statements b. Intuition Statements	3, 8, 18, 23 33, 38, 48, 53, 58, 63, 68, 73, 78, 83, 88, 93, 98, 103, 108, 113, 118, 23	13, 28, 43	25
Judging vs. Perceiving a. Judging Statements b. Perceiving Statements	4, 9, 14, 19, 24, 29, 34, 44, 49, 54, 59, 64, 69, 79, 84, 89, 94, 99, 104, 109, 114, 119, 124	39, 74	25
Extrinsic Motivation vs. Intrinsic Motivation a. Extrinsic Statements b. Intrinsic Statements	5, 10, 20, 25, 30, 35, 45, 50, 55, 60, 70, 75, 85, 90, 95, 100, 105, 110, 115, 120, 125	15, 40, 65, 80	25
Grand Total	108	17	125

Occupational Personality Inventory components are displayed in Table 1. Eighty-eight (108) items from relevant literature and seventeen (17) items from related studies were collected. In summary, a total of one hundred twenty-five (125) items were utilized in the first inventory.

Table 2. Initial Inventory and Distribution of Items

Questions	Domains
1 I am inspired to learn when	EX-IN
a. People are literally around me	Extraversion
b. People are not around me	Introversion
2 In accomplishing my task,	ST-NE
a. I know that my efforts will produce good results	Stability
b. I am in doubt if my efforts will be counted	Neuroticism
3 I like	SE-IN
a. To use established ways of doing things	Sensing
b. To create new ways of doing things	Intuition
4 When someone disagrees with my decision	JU-PE
a. I find it uncomfortable	Judging
b. I find it fine	Perceiving
5 My purpose for work is to	EM-IM
a. Earn money and buy stuffs	Extrinsic Motivation
b. Learn new skills and gain experience	Intrinsic Motivation

---Sample Items Only---

Table 2 shows the initial inventory and the distribution of items of the Occupational Personality Inventory per dichotomous domain. The initial inventory is composed of one hundred twenty-five (125) items. There were five (5) dichotomous domains in the initial inventory. The Extraversion vs. Introversion was comprised of twenty-five (25) items, Stability vs. Neuroticism has twenty-five (25) items, Sensing vs. Intuition has twenty-five (25) items, judging vs. Perceiving has twenty-five (25) items, and the Extrinsic vs. Intrinsic Motivation was composed of twenty-five (25) items. In the first inventory, each dichotomous item was distributed in turn. Extraversion vs. Introversion was the first item in the distribution sequence, followed by Stability vs. Neuroticism, Sensing vs. Intuition, Judging

vs. Perceiving, and Extrinsic vs. Intrinsic Motivation. Every item in the first inventory was arranged in the same, alternate order.

Validation of the Inventory

Following the creation of the Occupational Personality Inventory's first inventory, which had 125 items overall, the validation process was used. What a test was supposed to measure was measured by its validity. During the validation process, the researcher employed text analysis and face validation.

Face Validity

Following finalization, the items in each region of the inventory were allocated and placed appropriately. Expert recommendations were incorporated for the item placement. The items' apparent ability to measure what they were supposed to was determined using face validity.

To ensure an appropriate and suitable arrangement of the components, a table detailing the requirements for every domain of occupational personality was created.

Table 3. *Table of Specification of the Initial Inventory*

Occupational Personality		Item Number	Total
Extraversion vs. Introversion	Extraversion Statements	1, 6, 11, 16, 21, 26, 31, 36, 41, 46, 51, 56, 61, 66, 71, 76, 81, 86,	25
	Introversion Statements	91, 96, 101, 106, 111, 116, 121	
Stability vs. Neuroticism	Stability Statements	2, 7, 12, 17, 22, 27, 32, 37, 42, 47, 52, 57, 62, 67, 72, 77, 82, 87,	25
	b. Neuroticism Statements	92, 97, 102, 107, 112, 117, 122	
Sensory vs. Intuition	Sensory Statements	3, 8, 13, 18, 23, 28, 33, 38, 43, 48, 53, 58, 63, 68, 73, 78, 83, 88,	25
	Intuition Statements	93, 98, 103, 108, 113, 118, 23	
Judging vs. Perceiving	Judging Statements	4, 9, 14, 19, 24, 29, 34, 39, 44, 49, 54, 59, 64, 69, 74, 79, 84, 89,	25
	b. Perceiving Statements	94, 99, 104, 109, 114, 119, 124	
Extrinsic vs. Intrinsic Motivation	a. Extrinsic Statements	5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50, 55, 60, 65, 70, 75, 80, 85, 90,	25
	b. Intrinsic Statements	95, 100, 105, 110, 115, 120, 125	
Total Number of Items			125

Twenty-five (25) items for Extraversion vs. Introversion, twenty-five (25) for Stability vs. Neuroticism, twenty-five (25) for Sensory vs. Intuition, twenty-five (25) for Judging vs. Perceiving, and twenty-five (25) for Extrinsic vs. Intrinsic Motivation make up the first inventory of the Occupational Personality Inventory, which is displayed in Table 3. For the face and content authenticity, this was employed.

The Content Validity Ratio was utilized to ascertain the validity. The legitimate items that were kept and the invalid things that were removed were distinguished using CVR.

Content Validity

Following the face validation procedure, Lawshe's content validity was applied to the items. Each dichotomous domain item was assessed by the experts from three (3) to one (1). Three (3) points meant something was vital, two (2) said something was helpful but not essential, and one (1) meant something was not essential. To distinguish between valid and invalid items in the content analysis, the researcher employed the content validity ratio (CVR). The effectiveness with which a concept addressed each of the pertinent domains that it was intended to measure was assessed by the content analysis.

Following the completion of the content validity ratio, the valid and invalid items are displayed in Table 4. Twenty (20) of the items were valid for comparing extraversion and introversion; fourteen (14) were valid for comparing neuroticism and stability; twenty (20) were valid for comparing intuition and sensory perception; sixteen (16) were valid for comparing judging and perceiving; and fourteen (14) were valid for comparing extrinsic motivation to intrinsic motivation. Eighty-four (84) legitimate goods in total made up the first inventory. In general, the inventory's domains measure the things they are designed to measure.

The distribution of elements by domain in the final scale is displayed in Table 4. The Occupational Personality Inventory contained five (5) distinct dichotomous domains (OPI). These include judging versus perceiving, sensory versus intuition, stability versus neuroticism, extraversion versus introversion, and extrinsic versus intrinsic drive.

Table 4. Content Validity Ratio

Occupational Personality Inventory	Valid Items	Invalid Items	Total Number of Valid Items
Extraversion vs. Introversion	6, 11, 21, 31, 36, 41, 46, 51, 56, 61, 66, 76, 81, 86, 96, 101, 106, 111, 116, 121	1, 16, 26, 71, 91	20
Stability vs. Neuroticism	2, 7, 12, 27, 32, 42, 67, 77, 82, 92, 97, 102, 117, 122	17, 22, 37, 47, 52, 57, 62, 72, 87, 107, 112	14
Sensory vs. Intuition	3, 8, 13, 28, 38, 43, 53, 58, 63, 68, 73, 78, 83, 88, 93, 98, 103, 108, 113, 118	18, 23, 33, 48, 123	20
Judging vs. Perceiving	9, 34, 44, 49, 54, 64, 69, 74, 79, 84, 89, 99, 104, 109, 114, 119	4, 14, 19, 24, 29, 39, 59, 94, 124	16
Extrinsic vs. Intrinsic Motivation	5, 15, 25, 35, 45, 50, 65, 70, 75, 80, 90, 95, 100, 115	10, 20, 30, 40, 55, 60, 85, 105, 110, 120, 125	14
Total			84

Reliability Test

The second draft of the test was completed following the completion of the face validity and content analysis of the first inventory. The legitimate things were kept and the invalid ones were removed. Each dichotomous domain had fourteen (14) valid items included to ensure uniformity in the amount of items. Test re-test reliability was applied to the test's second draft. The test-retest design involved giving the same test to the same set of people twice to determine whether a construct was trustworthy over an extended period of time.

Table 5. Reliability Index of the OPI

Occupational Personality Inventory Domains	Test-Retest Reliability (Second Draft)	Test-Retest Reliability (Final Inventory)	Interpretation
Extraversion vs. Introversion	0.996	0.986	Excellent Reliability
Stability vs. Neuroticism	0.995	0.938	Excellent Reliability
Sensory vs. Intuition	0.994	0.949	Excellent Reliability
Judging vs. Perceiving	0.989	0.967	Excellent Reliability
Extrinsic vs. Intrinsic Motivation	0.995	0.917	Excellent Reliability

Table 5 demonstrates how a test-retest design was used to assess the second draft of the inventory's reliability. With a reliability index of 0.996, the extraversion vs. introversion comparison shows good dependability. With a reliability index of 0.995, the Stability vs. Neuroticism shows great reliability. With a reliability index of 0.994, Sensing vs. Intuition is shown to have great reliability. With a dependability value of 0.989, the Judging vs. Perceiving has very good reliability. With a reliability rating of 0.905, the extrinsic vs. intrinsic motivation is highly reliable. vs. Intrinsic Motivation has a reliability index of 0.905 indicating excellent reliability.

Retest testing was used to determine the final draft of the inventory's dependability after the second draft's reliability was established. In terms of extraversion against introversion, stability versus neuroticism, sensing versus intuition, judging versus perceiving, and extrinsic versus intrinsic motivation, the final draft's dependability indexes are 0.986, 0.938, 0.949, and 0.967, respectively. which all demonstrated outstanding dependability. A person with excellent reliability will see consistent results over time. Since the second draft and final inventory of the Occupational Personality Inventory has an excellent reliability index, this means that it will yield the same results over time.

Table 6. Final Inventory

Final Inventory	Domains
When the trainer is discussing,	EX-IN
1 a. I discuss it with my seatmate too	Extroversion
b. I process it in my mind by myself	Introversion
In accomplishing my task,	ST-NE
2 a. I know that my efforts will produce good results	Stability
b. I am in doubt if my efforts will be counted	Neuroticism
I like	SE-IN
3 a. To use established ways of doing things	Sensing
b. To create new ways of doing things	Intuition
When I wake up in the morning	JU-PE
4 a. I will organize my tasks for the day	Judging
b. I will start my day and see how it goes	Perceiving
My purpose for work is to	EM-IM
5 a. Earn money and buy stuffs	Extrinsic Motivation
b. Learn new skills and gain experience	Intrinsic Motivation

---Sample Items Only---

The distribution of items in the final draft of the Occupational Personality Inventory by dichotomous domain is displayed in Table 6. There are seventy (70) things in the final inventory. The final inventory contained five (5) dichotomous domains. There were fourteen (14) items in the Extraversion vs. Introversion, fourteen (14) in the Stability vs. Neuroticism, fourteen (14) in the Sensing vs. Intuition, fourteen (14) in the Judging vs. Perceiving, and fourteen (14) in the Extrinsic vs. Intrinsic Motivation. Each dichotomous item was distributed alternately in the final inventory. In the final inventory, each dichotomous item was distributed alternately. Extraversion vs. Introversion was the first item in the distribution sequence, followed by Stability vs. Neuroticism, sensing vs. Intuition, Judging vs. Perceiving, and Extrinsic vs. Intrinsic Motivation. Every item in the first inventory was arranged in the same, alternate order.

Standardization

Following the finalization of the test items, a manual with instructions and protocols for the appropriate administration, scoring, and interpretation of the test was created for the proctor or examiner. The test booklet mirrored the final inventory, which was included in the OPI manual. It also provided information on the test administration process, including timing, materials needed, pre-, during-, and post-test procedures, as well as manual scoring. The uniform administration and consistent scoring of the inventory were guaranteed by the standardization process.

Conclusions

The study's findings led to the following conclusions being made:

- The items of the created Occupational Personality Inventory evaluated the occupational personalities of Classic Baker Corporation personnel and represented various occupational personalities.
- Employees were discriminated against based on their occupational personalities according to the items in the scale.
- Every item in the inventory met statistical validity requirements.
- The reliability index of the Occupational Personality Inventory (OPI) is very good.

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